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**DIGITAL INDIA AND ELECTORAL MANIPULATION: AN
ETHICAL AND POLITICAL ANALYSIS**

Annotation: The research aims to discover the effects of Digital India in electoral manipulation in India. Several examples of electoral manipulation have been presented through the discussion as evidence. For instance, the usage of social media and digital content by Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has been mentioned from the 2019 general election. A systematic review has been performed by selecting 11 peer-reviewed journals and articles emphasizing on the initiative of Digital India that has significantly impacted the political integrity of India. Cybersecurity and public awareness have remained as constant concerns of this political landscape. The involvement of ECI and IAMAI has been proven to be effective to strengthen the legal frameworks and code of conduct.

Key words: Digital India, Electoral Manipulation, Political Integrity, Public Awareness, Digital and Media Literacy.

Introduction

The research focuses on exploring the "Digital India" that aims to empower Indian citizens through digital connectivity while presenting unique challenges in electoral manipulation. The political aspect of India is often vulnerable to manipulation through digital transformation, posing potential risks. This can be attributed to the increased reliance on various digital platforms and the vast amounts of public data that are exploited in many ways. It also raises a significant concern about the fairness and integrity of elections in India, which will also be discussed using examples. Hence, the research will provide an idea of how initiatives of Digital India intersect with manipulation in Indian elections, with safeguards.

Background and Problem Statement

Background

The functions of Digital India can offer potential benefits to improve electoral processes in India. Digital tools and technologies have the potential to increase the accessibility of information as well as the efficiency of elections (Hickok, 2018). However, it often introduces complexities related to electoral manipulation, which can degrade the political stability and outcomes in India. A multi-pronged approach is essential to be taken to address such complex challenges involving robust regulatory and legal frameworks. For instance, Bedi (2019) has revealed that India had 1.1 billion smartphone users, and political content remained high in demand during the season of the election. Political parties in India build new communication strategies using digital platforms to share information and add more opportunities for the parties.

Problem statement

The social media presence of top politicians in India can affect each other's public image. The loss of image and public trust during the election can harm the electoral integrity of various political parties (Mehta, 2019). In contrast, digital platforms have increased the engagement level of one politician per tweet over time, yet the cumulative engagement metrics for another politician might remain higher

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during this period. Besides, page likes on Facebook and interactions between 2018 and 2019 of Indian political leaders and the public show their bigger follower base and potential influence. Hence, such statistics demonstrate how digital platforms can differentiate the influence of politicians in India and raise complexities during election times.

Previous Literature

Digital politics in India regarding the general elections

The general election of 2019 was the first national election that took place in a true digital consumption society. During this election, over half of the voting population had easy access to digital pathways that significantly manipulated the election process (Buragohain, 2019). The digital data-consumption society of India between 2016 and 2019 has been held responsible for the societal paradigm shift during this general election. Digital division in Indian society has become prominent as internet users have gone up by eight times from May 2014 (65.3 million) to May 2019 (581.51 million), according to the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India in 2019.

A major public debate took place in the general election of 2019, where valuable social media companies such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Google, Twitter, and the respective companies agreed to follow a “voluntary code of ethics”. The *Internet & Mobile Association of India (IAMAI)* submitted this code to the *Election Commission of India (ECI)* in March 2019 (Mehta, 2019) (Mehta, 2019). This initiative has shown mixed results; for instance, Facebook launched the "Candidate Connect" initiative to share accurate political information to help citizens learn about different candidates in the election. Google News also took an initiative named the "Poll-check" program to constitute training sessions for selected journalists for verification, fact-checking, and data visualization (Sen et al. 2019).

Elements of Digital India that are causing electoral manipulation in India

Digital platforms often result in disinformation or misinformation campaigns for an amplified reach through AI-generated content. AI uses voice clones or deepfakes that can mislead voters and manipulate the opinions of politicians or the public on a huge scale (Mirchandani, 2018). Digital platforms leverage vast amounts of public data, such as demographics, past voting behaviour, or social media activity, that can be analyzed using AI for micro-targeting a specific voter group. It involves highly customized propaganda to tailor messages for citizens according to individual preferences. However, as argued by Cheeseman et al. (2018), data breaches and voter surveillance are crucial components of data leaks. A few government initiatives, such as the linking of Aadhaar to voter ID, can compromise the privacy of Indian citizens, especially the voting population.

Figure 1: Pillars of Digital India; Source: Influenced by Mirchandani, 2018

Figure 1 depicts different pillars of Digital India initiatives that comprise broadband highways, access to phones, public awareness, e-governance, and the respective. These factors significantly affect the information-sharing process that helps citizens make voting decisions. Electoral digital systems are prone to cyberattacks and hacking, which is a significant factor in vulnerabilities (Mirchandani, 2018). Indian political candidates and parties remain susceptible to phishing attacks to steal sensitive credentials and information.

Countermeasures that is effective in decreasing electoral manipulation for Digital India

Threats of electoral manipulation are being countered by proposed and implemented measures by the ECI and various stakeholders. According to Ziad et al. (2014), the ECI has mandated a shift from a voluntary code to a “*Model Code of Conduct*” for social media, following a set of guidelines for reporting mechanisms. Legal and regulatory frameworks involve accountability in digital platforms regarding targeted campaigns and political advertising to adopt international standards of rights. Moreover, the current status of the *Personal Data Protection Bill* is still evolving to strengthen data protection laws and regulations. The Indian government has also mandated an AI-based monitoring system to remove deepfake videos and political advertisements (Zhang et al. 2016). Auditability has also been ensured by incorporating “*Voter Verifiable Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT)*”, ERO-NET, e-EPIC, cVIGIL, and the respective improvements to enhance security measures.

Research Gap

Previous literature papers on electoral manipulation through digital transformation lack emphasis on specific digital initiatives of a country. Existing papers mainly concentrate on e-voting systems, social media trends during elections, and foreign electoral interference using digital tools and platforms (Cheeseman et al. 2018; Buragohain, 2019; & Sen et al. 2019). However, a single focus on a digital initiative and its impact on the elections, along with the public image of political leaders, can offer more specific knowledge that is currently lacking in existing literary sources. Therefore, the current research aims to address this gap to understand the underlying factors and their impacts on election manipulation so that countermeasures can be applied.

Research Aim and Objectives

The research aims to critically assess the concept of Digital India, causing electoral manipulation through an ethical and political examination. The objectives of the research is to understand the impact of the Digital India initiative in the general elections of India and to identify factors resulting in electoral manipulation through Digital India. It also focusses to point out safeguards and countermeasures to reduce electoral manipulation due to the emerging Digital India concept

Research question

How is Digital India and the electoral manipulation of India connected?

Methodology

A systematic review will be followed in this research, which encompasses a planned stage of literature review. It has resulted in a meaningful exploration and discussion of the Indian political landscape by applying digital platforms (Jukna & Sergeev, 2013). Various databases, such as newspaper articles, authentic journals, and government websites of India, have been accessed to gather accurate information. The accessed databases include ProQuest, ScienceDirect, Wiley, Elsevier, and the respective ones as they are recognized for being authentic. Only relevant information on digital initiatives of Indian politics and their impacts on the manipulation of politics have been included for the execution of this research.

Keywords	AND/OR	Keywords	AND/OR	Keywords
Digital India	AND	Digital connectivity	AND	Electoral manipulation
Electoral integrity	AND	Digital platforms	OR	Safeguards and countermeasures
Communication strategies	OR	Political opportunities	AND	Social media platforms
Accurate information sharing	AND	Increased follower base	OR	Digital division of India

Table 1: Boolean search results; Source: Influenced by Lame, 2019

Table 1 mentions the effective keywords that have been applied to find only relevant articles and sources from the accessed databases. Using these combinations of words with a filter of the year of

publication has helped in narrowing down the search results and increasing the accuracy of extracted information.

Figure 2: PRISMA diagram; Source: Influenced by Xiao & Watson, 2019

Figure 2 is the demonstration of the PRISMA diagram that works as a screening process of selecting the ultimate number of literary sources. The above diagram mentions that 11 peer-reviewed journals and articles have been chosen to conduct the systematic review process. Several criteria have been applied for the final selection, such as the relevance of the content, DOI, language, and peer-reviewed (Xiao & Watson, 2019). Therefore, a thematic analysis has been conducted to refer to the Indian political aspects that are currently impacted by the Digital India initiative.

Results

Authors	Codes	Themes
Neyazi et al. (2016) Ahmed et al. (2016) Mukherjee (2019) Poushter (2014)	Technological solutions, Digital India in elections, data protection, election infrastructure, and personal data of voters	“Theme 1: Indian politicians use digital platforms to reach the maximum voting population and influence them through social media content”
Das & Patel (2017) Kedar (2015) Kumar (2019) Singh et al. (2019)	AI-driven content, algorithm bias, discrimination against voter groups, surrogate advertising	“Theme 2: Social media campaigns and cybersecurity are fundamental components affecting the Digital India initiative in Indian political integrity”
Mihailidis & Thevenin (2013) Shen et al. (2019) Nenadić (2019)	Voter education campaigns, digital activities, public awareness, digital literacy, online content, and identifying misinformation	“Theme 3: Media literacy and public awareness are crucial steps determining the effects of Digital India on political manipulation”

Table 2: Axial coding

Thematic analysis

Theme 1: Indian politicians use digital platforms to reach the maximum voting population and influence them through social media content

Indian politicians have started using digital platforms to connect with the target audience during elections. According to Neyazi et al. (2016), digital platforms allow a direct engagement with voters rather than traditional media. For instance, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has been using social media platforms since 2014 to propagate its philosophy and ideology, set political agendas, and mobilize public opinion. It has directly led to a coalition government in the general election of 2019. The Indian National Congress party was the main opposition party of the BJP in 2019, which also heavily invested in digital political campaigns to continuously engage with the citizens during the election (Ahmed et al. 2016).

Figure 3: Sharing political opinions by Indian citizens; Source: Influenced by Poushter, 2014

Figure 3 expresses the survey results conducted by Poushter (2014) between December 2013 and January 2014 in India about the usage of social media by citizens to share their political opinions. Their survey response has demonstrated that 90% of social networking users use different social media platforms by 90% to stay connected with their friends and families. However, only 35% of Indian citizens used social media to share their views on politics, which showcases the fear of getting into complicated situations regarding politics on online platforms (Mukherjee, 2019). Yet, technological expansion and the Digital India movement have been integrated into the democratic practices of the Indian election process.

On another note, digital platforms come with varied content creation and formats that include text posts and updates, images, infographics, or videos. For example, memes have become increasingly popular over time referring to satirical and humorous messaging that emotionally connects with the audience, spreading virally (Neyazi et al. 2016). India has multilingual diversity, and thus, political parties use AI tools to translate speeches into various local and regional languages to engage with voters on a personal level. It also allows grassroots mobilization, such as through creating extensive networks, such as WhatsApp groups, to disseminate daily political content to often manipulate the audience.

Theme 2: Social media campaigns and cybersecurity are fundamental components affecting the Digital India initiative in Indian political integrity

Social media campaigns and cybersecurity are two interconnected elements in the context of political integrity in India. As per the view of Kedar (2015), political communication has been democratized

with the rise of social media content that has introduced vulnerabilities to political integrity. Social media is seen to affect political integrity by manipulating public opinions, such as through the development of false narratives and attacking opponents by spreading rumours. Furthermore, AI has become a sophisticated means of deep faking that often fabricates the truth and manipulates the target audience (Kumar, 2019). As a result, advisories have been issued by the ECI to label AI-generated content used in political campaigns.

Figure 4: Cybercrime rate in India 2011-2015; Source: Influenced by Das & Patel, 2017

Cybercrime in India is constantly rising, as represented in Figure 4 from a survey of 2011 and 2015. The survey was carried out by Das & Patel (2017) and found that the number of cybercrimes registered in 2013 was 4356, which increased to 8045 in 2015. In comparison to the registered cases, the rate of arrest was low during this time, as the number was 2098 in 2013, which increased and reached 5102 in 2015. Cybercrime is also increasing and negatively imposing challenges on political agendas through hate speech and polarization. Similarly, Singh et al. (2019) have also supported this idea by stating that social media amplifies “echo chambers” where information is exposed to individuals and confirms their existing beliefs.

Social media or digital content created by political parties in India often lacks transparency, especially in political advertising. It is challenging to track the sources of the content and required funding when it involves *proxy* pages and unverified accounts (Das & Patel, 2017). It reduces accountability for generating and spreading content that jeopardizes political integrity. Besides, social media platforms are also exploited by adversarial foreign interference, influencing election outcomes. Therefore, it shows the significance of promoting a voluntary code of ethics while using social media platforms to regulate encrypted platforms.

Theme 3: Media literacy and public awareness are crucial steps in determining the effects of Digital India on political manipulation

Media literacy is found to be a critical element in overcoming the issues of political manipulation in terms of Digital India. The differences between manipulative content and its credibility can be

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addressed by improving media literacy (Shen et al. 2019). Moreover, it also helps to increase public awareness regarding the manipulative content that political parties often create during elections. For example, the BJP promoted its decisive political agendas in 2019 through Hindutva, which is a political ideology that primarily targets Hinduism and airbrushes the secular image in India, manipulating the audience (Nenadić, 2019). Their goal was to create a *Hindu Rashtra*, India is a diverse country it was essential to be included in the social media campaigns.

Figure 5: Framework of media literacy as a core component of engaging with citizens; Source: Influenced by Mihailidis & Thevenin, 2013

Figure 5 represents the media literacy framework that plays a vital role in the social media campaigns of Indian political parties to engage with the audience. The findings of Mihailidis & Thevenin (2013) have suggested that participatory, collaborative, expressive, and critical competencies are the core media literacy elements. These competencies create a critical thinker, a communicator, and an agent for social change. Therefore, both political leaders and citizens need to have media literacy to think about the information shared through social media before believing it. On the other hand, Nenadić (2019) has argued by stating that comprehending media bias is important to distinguishing objective reporting of the media. As a result, critical thinking can be promoted among Indian citizens who are manipulated by politicians during elections using digital platforms.

Discussion

Themes	Results
Theme 1	Digital India approach has shown the effectiveness of social media platforms in creating social groups of people so that they can be influenced by Indian political leaders.
Theme 2	Using digital media comes with the threat of data breaches as it involves demographic data such as the Aadhaar numbers of the voting population.
Theme 3	It has connected political manipulation and Digital India by finding public awareness as an important step in safeguarding Indian citizens during and after elections.

Table 3: Summary of results

The thematic analysis has focused on answering the research question by interpreting data related to the interconnection between Digital India and electoral manipulation. For instance, the first theme of the study has critically assessed how Indian politicians use digital tools and platforms to target the voting population (Rahul, 2016). They prioritize generating powerful content and spreading it through social media platforms to reach a wider range of the target audience. On another note, another theme has pinpointed how impactful cybersecurity threats and social media content are in maintaining political integrity. Other social media and personal information are also used by political parties to use social media more effectively (Vaishnav et al. 2019). Hence, it has established a connection between the Digital India approach and political manipulation. Finally, the third theme involves a deeper insight into media literacy among Indian citizens that can positively improve how they perceive political content on social media (Avgerou et al. 2019).

Conclusion

The research has been initiated to debate a less explored area of research regarding Digital India lead and its effects on electoral manipulation. A secondary review has been conducted to delve deeper into the prospects of Digital India and how it has impacted the general election in 2019. Existing literary sources have projected ideas on digital platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Google that are effectively used for information sharing among Indian citizens. The regulatory frameworks by ECI and the code of conduct proposed by IAMAI have backed up the importance of following ethics in using digital platforms for political purposes.

Future Scope and Recommendations

Future scope

This particular research has incorporated information from a limited period, which can be further extended in future studies. This research will work as a foundation for future research, as digital transformation in India has improved drastically after 2019 (Avgerou et al. 2019). Besides, the social media campaigns and their approaches have also changed during this period to maintain a positive public image of the politicians. The legal precautions in political parties have improved over time to strengthen their position in society due to the changing perceptions of the voting population in India, which can be emphasized in future research.

Recommendations

The challenges of electoral manipulation can be addressed by strengthening regulatory enforcement, especially for political advertising. Content moderation policies can be recommended to be stricter for removing manipulated content as they shape the voting decisions of the citizens (Mirchandani, 2018). AI-based content must be labelled to ensure they do not mislead voters in the context of the elections.

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